

In the case of phosphorus determination by the above method it has been observed that for full reduction with stannous chloride and development of blue colour there should not be any dissolved oxygen in the solution. The results obtained in the various experiments are summarised in the Table 1.

TABLE-1

	pH	Room Temp °C	Zn (g mole/litre) × 10 ⁶	Phosphate (g mole/litre) × 10 ⁶
Zinc phosphate Crystalline	4.95	24	64	43
	6.60	25	3.2	2.2
	8.5	25	0.86	1.16
Colloidal	5.0	34	69	46
	6.65	26	2.4	1.6
	8.5	30	0.87	1.16
Lab. sample	5.0	34	67	48
	6.85	34	2.7	1.8
	8.5	24	0.86	1.16

The results show that the solubility of zinc phosphate is almost the same within experimental limits of error and independent of the physical form of the sample but dependent on pH. PO₄³⁻ ions which, because they have to satisfy equilibrium criteria, will pass on to other complex species. Phosphoric acid is a tribasic acid the three equilibrium constants⁶ being pK₁=2.1, pK₂=7.2, and pK₃=12.3.

The concentrations of PO₄³⁻, HPO₄²⁻ and H₂PO₄¹⁻ at any pH may be calculated with the help of the following expressions :

$$\begin{aligned}
 [H_3PO_4] &= CF^{-1} \\
 [H_2PO_4^-] &= CK_1[H^+]^{-1} F^{-1} \\
 [HPO_4^{2-}] &= CK_1 K_2 [H^+]^{-2} F^{-1} \\
 [PO_4^{3-}] &= CK_1 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^{-3} F^{-1} \\
 \text{where } F &= 1 + K_1 [H^+]^{-1} + K_1 K_2 [H^+]^{-2} \\
 &+ K_1 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^{-3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, at pH 5, most of the phosphate is in the form H₂PO₄⁻; at pH 6.65, H₂PO₄⁻ constitutes 80% of the total phosphate, the rest being HPO₄²⁻; at pH 8.5, 95% of the total phosphate consists of HPO₄²⁻ and about 5% of H₂PO₄⁻.

The solid phase is constituted of Zn₃(PO₄)₂. In solution the following ionic species are likely to be present depending on the pH.

In addition, the system has to satisfy the equilibrium⁷ :

On the basis of what has been stated above the ionic species present in solution at pH 5 are those given by equations (1) and (2), and since equation (4) predominates at this pH no Zn(OH)₂ is formed. At pH 6.5, the equations (1), (2), (3) and (4) hold good and the ionic species mentioned therein are present. At pH's 5 and 6.5, therefore, the ratio of Zn to P in solution should be 1.5. At pH 8.5, the ionic species mentioned in equations (3) and (5) predominate, such that the solid phase is constituted of Zn₃(PO₄)₂, ZnHPO₄ and Zn(OH)₂. Because of the formation of Zn(OH)₂ the ratio of Zn to P in solution will be less than 1.5. Since the stability constants of Zn₃(PO₄)₂, ZnHPO₄ and ZnPO₄ are not known the relative proportions of each cannot be quantitatively evaluated.

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Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) with 2'-Hydroxy-3'-Bromo-4-Methoxy-5'-Methylchalcone Oxime

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IN continuation of our earlier¹⁻⁷ work on 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime (HMMCO) as the new analytical reagents for Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Fe(III) we report here the solvent extraction studies of Pd(II) with 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime (HB-MMCU).

The purpose of this paper is to establish the scope of application of 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime (HBMMCO) to solvent extraction of the palladium. The work described below has shown its potential utility for the said purpose. This paper deals with the various aspects of Pd(II)-HBMMCO extraction studies in water-isobutanol system.

Experimental

Reagent and Solutions: Standard palladium perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolving chloride free palladium hydroxide obtained from the 1 g of palladium chloride (Johnson Matthey) in perchloric acid and was standardized gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime⁸.

The reagent, HBMMCO, was synthesized by refluxing 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone⁹ with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in acetic acid and purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol to get the m. p. 198° (Found: C, 56.3%; H, 4.54%; N, 3.96%; Br, 22.0%; Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆NO₃Br, C, 56.23%; H, 4.42%; N, 3.87%, Br, 22.07%). 0.002M HBMMCO in isobutanol was used for extraction studies. Fresh solution in distilled isobutanol was used.

Perchloric acid stock solutions of interfering ions containing 0.01-0.1 mg of ion per ml, were used. All other chemical used were of A. R. (BDH) quality.

Apparatus: Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Beckman model DU 2 spectrophotometer and 10 mm quartz cells. The pH adjustments were made with a ELICO pH meter model LI-10.

General procedure: Aliquot containing less than 140 µg of Pd(II) was adjusted to pH 1.0-3.0 by perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide (keeping the ionic strength 0.2M by NaClO₄.) The solution was shaken with 10 ml of 0.002M HBMMCO in isobutanol for 15 min. After equilibration the organic layer was separated and absorbance was noted against the reagent as a blank at 390 nm, the wavelength of maximum absorption. Pd(II) extracted from the calibration curve, as usual.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra: The absorption spectra of solution of the palladium(II)-HBMMCO complex (140 µg, Pd) against a similarly processed reagent as a blank exhibits a peak of absorption at 390 nm. The molar absorptivity of complex is 3.2×10^4 .

Effect of pH: The extraction of palladium (140 µg) was studied in the pH region 0.5-8.0. Extraction was quantitative in the pH range 1.0-3.0. Below

and above this pH, extraction was incomplete and there was no extraction above pH 6.0.

Effect of reagent concentration: Palladium was extracted with different volumes and concentrations of reagent varying from 1.0×10^{-4} - 1.0×10^{-2} M over the pH range of 1.0-3.0. The results show that a single extraction with 5.0×10^{-3} M reagent suffice for quantitative extraction of palladium. There was no significant enhancement in the extraction of palladium with higher reagent concentration.

Effect of metal ion concentration: The effect of metal ion concentration has been investigated on the Pd extraction at different pH and the study ruled out the possibility of polymerization in the working range of metal concentration.

Effect of ionic strength: The distribution of palladium was studied at various concentration of sodium perchlorate (0.2-40M) at pH 2.3, and it was observed that the extent of extraction remains same upto 1.0M NaClO₄. However, extraction decrease at above 1.0M of NaClO₄.

Effect of solvents: Amongst the various non-aqueous solvents tried, viz. benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, isoamyl alcohol, n-butanol and isobutanol etc., isobutanol was found to be most efficient.

Time of shaking: Pd-HBMMCO system was equilibrated for times varying from 0.5-30 min. The extraction was quantitative at about 12-15 min and hence a time of 15 min was arbitrarily chosen for the entire extraction studies.

Beer's law, sensitivity and colour stability: The Pd(II)-HBMMCO system obeyed Beer's law over the concentration range 1.4-42.0 µg Pd(II) per ml of isobutanol. The effective working range according to Ringbom curve is 3.0-20.0 µg Pd(II) per ml of isobutanol. The Sandell's sensitivity¹⁰ of the system was found to be 0.033 µg Pd cm⁻². The Pd(II)-HBMMCO complex imparts constant absorption for 3 days.

Effect of foreign ions: Many foreign ions were tested for interferences. The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ion needed to causes $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of Pd(II). Tolerance limits for diverse ions (in µg) are Ag⁺ (1600), Al³⁺ (2100), Cd²⁺ (5000), Co²⁺ (8000), Cr³⁺ (500), Cu²⁺ (11000), Fe³⁺ (1900), Fe²⁺ (1500), Ca²⁺ (2100), Hg²⁺ (16000), In³⁺ (590), Mn²⁺ (1200), Ni²⁺ (10000), Pb²⁺ (300), Rh³⁺ (400), Ru³⁺ (600), Ti⁴⁺ (1200), VO²⁺ (4500), Zn²⁺ (7500), ZrO²⁺ (None), F⁻ (20000), Cl⁻ (40000), Br⁻ (46000), NO₃⁻ (50000), NO₂⁻ (4000), SO₄²⁻ (60000), SO₃²⁻ (32000), B₄O₇²⁻ (10000), Mo₇O₂₄⁶⁻ (1000), WO₄²⁻ (4000), PO₄²⁻ (5000), SCN⁻ (5500), C₂O₄²⁻ (3200), Tart³⁺ (2000), Cit³⁻ (2500), EDTA⁴⁻ (None).

Precision and accuracy: The absorbance obtained

